

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B358
 Date: 22 April 2008
 Take Off: 08:24:31Z
 Landing: 10:52:14Z
 Flight Time 2h 28

Campaign: ACAS

Operating Area: Rotterdam – North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Trainer 1	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
9	Trainer 2	Steve Devereau	FAAM
10	CVI	Paul Barret	Met Office
11	ACAS Training	Thomas Hamburger	DLR
12	ACAS Training	Karin Ardon	TAU (Tel Aviv University)
13	ACAS Training	Daniel Perez	CEAMA (University of Granada)
14	ACAS Training	Benjamin Aouizerats	METEO France
15	ACAS Training	Livio Belegante	National Institute of Optoelectronics
16	ACAS Training	Helen Macintyre	U of Leeds

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B358
 Date: 22 April 2008
 Project: ACAS
 Location: Rotterdam, N Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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081932		Start-Up	0.11 kft	002	51'57.00N, 4'26.13E
081938		ASP	0.11 kft	334	Open
082431		T/O	0.99 kft	057	Rotterdam
083337	083645	Profile 1	3.1 - 1.1 kft	261	3k'-1k' on QNH 1009hPa
0840		Video			Start FFC & DFC1
083646	084013	Run 1	1.1 kft	262	1k', QNH 1009hPa
083838		Event	1.1 kft	261	Ships plume
084013	084119	Profile 2	1.1 - 0.61 kft	261	500'
084119	085250	Run 2	0.61 - 0.68 kft	267	500'
084818		Event	0.58 kft	302	QNH 1010hPa
085423	085952	Profile 3	0.13 - 3.1 kft	010	From 50', 500fpm
085952	090601	Run 3	3.1 kft	005	3k', A-B
090602	090743	Profile 4	3.1 - 4.1 kft	006	3k'-4k'
090944	091649	Profile 4	4.1 - 9.0 kft	173	4k'-FL90, 1000fpm
091850	092424	Run 4	9.0 kft	344	A-B
092424	093035	Profile 5	9.0 - 15.0 kft	358	
093138		Event	15.0 kft	275	Zero Nevzorov
093214	093831	Profile 6	15.0 - 12.0 kft	260	500fpm
094229	094636	Run 5	12.7 kft	100	In Dust Layer
094803	095012	Run 6	13.7 kft	098	Above Dust - almost
095054	095256	Run 7	14.5 kft	097	Above Dust now
095344	095912	Profile 7	14.5 - 9.0 kft	175	1000fpm
100047	100449	Run 8	9.0 kft	003	C-D
100248		Video	9.0 kft	359	Change Tapes
100449	101104	Profile 8	4.9 - 3.1 kft	174	3k', QNH 1010hPa
101204	101615	Run 9	3.1 kft	002	3k', C-D
103000	104050	Profile 9	16.0 - 4.6 kft	160	1500fpm
105214		Land	0.10 kft	147	Rotterdam
105343		ASP	0.10 kft	238	Closed
105705		Shutdown	0.10 kft	326	51'56.98N, 4'26.15E

B358 Track 22-APR-08

Sortie Brief – ACAS Summer School ; De-Bilt, 21 – 24 April 2008

Flight B 358

Date: Tues 22nd April 2008

Mission Scientist: Dave Kindred

Briefing: 0530 UT (0730 local)

Take off: 0830 UT (1030 local)

Land: 1050 UT (1250 local)

Aim: To observe atmospheric and aerosol properties in the boundary layer and free troposphere in two different air masses.

Location: Southern North Sea

Weather conditions: Easterly winds, clear sky, chance of low cloud.

Key instruments: Aerosol properties and trace gas instruments.

Sortie Detail:

#	Time (Z)	Manoeuvre	Duration
1.		Leave Rotterdam. Travel west at 1000 ft. Ship tracks near Felixstowe.	35 min
2.		Stacked-vertical profile from 1000ft – FL90. a. Run at 3,000ft (6 min) (A => B) b. Run at FL90 (5 min) (A => B)	28 min
3.		Profile to locate dust layer (estimated at FL120) climbing at 1000fpm. Run at 1000ft above the dust layer (4 min) and a run within it (5 min). All this is done travelling north.	14 min
4.		Stacked-vertical profile from FL120 – 3,000ft at location further north than the first one. a. Run at FL90 (5 min) (C => D) b. Run at 3,000ft (6 min) (D => C)	23 min
5.		Return transit to Rotterdam.	40 min
6.			Total time: 2hrs 20 min
7.			
8.			
9.			
10.			

MISSION SCIENTIST DEBRIEFING SHEET

Date: Tuesday 22nd April 2008

Flight Number: B358

This sortie was the first (of 3) of the ACAS (EUFAR-funded) Summer School flights, each one planned for about 2 hr 20 mins, and each one with 6-7 European PhD-level students joining the FAAM crew.

The flight was generally successful in terms of the sortie brief aims & objectives. After T/O from Rotterdam at 0824z (R/W 06), we transited at 3000 ft until clear of the Dutch coast, then performed low-level runs (500 ft – 1000 ft ASL) to monitor ship plumes and generally low-level aerosol. Once just off the E. Anglian coast (near Felixtowe), we headed North and performed S&L runs at 3000 ft and FL 090 (A<--> B) – 5-6 mins each – separated by profile ascent sections.

Thereafter we climbed to FL050 (Profile P5), and worked an aerosol/dust layer (barely visible to the naked eye, some particles seen on PCASP & CVI), with a run in this layer (FL127 – 4 minutes) followed by a run above (nominally) this layer (FL 137 for 2 minutes, then FL145 for 2 minutes). We then descended to low level, stopping for S&L runs again at FL090 and 3000 ft (C<-->D, about 4 mins each), in a similar area to AB previously.

Finally, a rapid climb to FL 160 was made before commencing a slow rate descent back towards base (Rotterdam), landing at 1052 z (flight duration 2 h 28 m).

Skies were clear, apart from 6/8 -7/8 Ci/Cs cloud at high level, tending to thicken towards the west, and in time during the sortie. Winds were generally light, E or SE'ly at low/medium levels, moderate NW'ly above. A significant top to the haze/pollution/heavy aerosol layer at around 4200 ft – 4500 ft was noted, trapping this 'dirty' air below an isothermal/inversion layer and strong hydrolapse.

A useful, interesting sortie as an education/training flight, over-running by about 8 minutes from briefing timings. Instrumentation worked generally well, and this should therefore provide a very good data-set for the ACAS students.

DRK
23/04/08

[Group I]

ACAS
[EVAIR SUMMER SCHOOL]

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B358** Date **22/4/08** Name **DRK** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0824			→		T/o Rotterdam (QFE 1058) RW 06
0826					Climb to 3000' initially, to clear Rotterdam traffic Hazy low level Only cloud is 6/8 thin Ci well above.
08		At 3000'			[Problems with internet explorer]
0835		Require to descend			3000' ↓ 1000' on M/S (lapping)
08337	P1 ↓	3000'			Start P1 ↓ Hazy ! Much shipping below (egs 8fted)
083646	END P1 / START	1000'			End P1 / start R1. QNH = 1059
083638		1000'	→		Crossing ship plane. (COSCO) 4 sec delay on phone. C. Physics kit (making)
084013		END R1	1000'	/ START	P2 ↓ to 500'.
084119	START R2 / END P2				Start R2 at 500'
0843					Turning 5 L to pick up plane/wake from Evergreen cargo
0851					QNH = 1010 (RADALT checks)
085250	END R2				END R2 at 500'. Hazy 7/8 Ci above. (thicker now).
085423	START P3 / 50'		005°		Start P3 50' ↑ [Heading N now] Climb to 3000' at 500'/min
085952	END P3 / START R3	3000'			End P3 / Start R3 at 3000' (PT ALPHA) Still hazy at this height (+ above) & below.
090602		3000'			End R3 3000' / Start PK Continue on this heading to 4000', then turn & return to PFA, climbing 4000' / 2000'

m. 20 sec.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.358** Date 22/4/08 Name DEK Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
090743	P4				Interrupt P4 at 4000' turn \leftarrow onto reciprocal (S) Haze tops looks to be ~ 3600' - 3800'.
090944	P4 \nearrow	4000' @ 175			
0911		5500' \rightarrow			Haze layer now well below. Only 7/8 above.
091649	END P4 Turning \curvearrowright			onto NORTH again	End of P4 at FL090, turn to do next M/Sc LAPTOP Now OK \checkmark FL090.
091850	START R4	FL090	343	52.24N 2.00E	Start R4 at FL090 A \rightarrow B Temp -2.6C ; DPT -27.3C. HX27 Below; 7/8 Ci / Cs above. (thicker to W)
092424	END R4 START R5	FL090			at 'B' END R4 / START P5 at 1000'/min.
093035	END P5 START P6	FL150	003	53.12N 2.00E	End P5 Commence P6 \searrow Descends thro dust-layer
093214	START P6	FL150	260		End P6 at FL120 Turning / manoeuvring in area to avoid Air Traffic
093831	END P6 START R5	FL120	257		Start R5 at FL127 (in dust / aerosol plane) Some particles (v few) 1 or 2 per 2 seconds (thru dust layer)
094636	END R5 START R6	FL127			End R5, start climb to FL137 (to be 1000' above dust layer)
094843	START R6	FL137			END R6 Start R6 (8h) a few dust particles here so / climb another 200'
095012	(1000' above dust)				END R6, climb to FL145 V. LITTLE DUST! 8000' VISIBILITY
095054	START R7	FL145			Start R7 at FL145.
095256	END R7				End R7 at FL145.
095344	START P7	FL145	178		Start P7 \searrow 1000'/min

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B358** Date **22/4/08** Name **DEK** Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095912	P7	FL090			} End P7, turn onto N for next run at FL090 S → N (C → D)
100047	NOT R28	FL090			Start Run 8, C → D (heading N)
100449	R28	FL090	359°		} End R8, turning ↓ Descent (NOT profile) to 3000'.
101100					Start Run 9 New at 3000', turning ↙
101204	NOT R29	3000'			Start Run 9 (QNH 1010) NOT
					} 'TECHNOGRAM' v. large change in Dew Point ~ 4500' (isothermal above) in this area. Back into significant haze layer at this height (trapped below isoth/ hydrologic layer)
101615	END R9	3000'			End Run 9, climb & return to Rotterdam
10					
1022					New at FL160 & heading ESE back to Rotterdam base.
102500	FL 160	DESIGN TRANSIT	109°	52° 54' N 5° 36' E	} Haze layer well below. 7/8 Ci/Cs above (thickened during flight)
103000	FL 160	"	ESE		START FINAL PROFILE 9, inbound
103600		Passing thro'		FL160	on descent into Rotterdam.
104050	END P9	4500'	E		End P. 9
1044	→	4300'			Returning into haze/smog layer now.
1045		3100'			} 8th. (mech) turbulence as crossing Dutch coast here
1046/7	→				
1053		LAND		ROTTERDAM.	(2406)

0824
2428 m.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B358

Date: 22/04/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0`	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:33:37	900	0.11	2	1	1											Start Profile 1 from 3000'	
08:35:10	1200	0.11		1	1											2000'	
08:36:44																END OF profile 1 & start Run 1.1 @ 1000'	
08:37:00	1500	0.10		2	1												
08:39:00	1400	0.10		3	3												
08:40:12																End of Run 1 & start Profile 2 from 1000'	
08:41:19																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ 500'	
08:42:00	1500	0.10		10	10												
08:44:00	5000	0.10	3	10	10												
08:46:00	1600	0.09		10	10												
08:48:00	1500	0.09	4	10	10												
08:50:00	1600	0.09		10	10												
08:52:48																End of Run	
08:54:24	1400	0.09	5	30	30											Start Profile 3 from 50'	
08:56:25	1200	0.10	6	1	1											1000'	
08:58:14	1150	0.10		1	1											2000'	
08:59:53																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 3 @3000'	
09:00:00	1100	0.10		2	2												
09:02:00	1300	0.10		1	1												
09:04:00	1200	0.10		1	1												
09:06:01	1120	0.10		1	1											End of Run 3 & start Profile 4 from 3000'	
09:07:25	750	0.10		1	1											FL040	
09:11:12	100	0.09		50	1											FL050	
09:12:15	100	0.08		1	1											FL060	
09:13:36	120	0.09		1	1											FL070	
09:14:45	130	0.09		1	1											FL080 SID 2 showed stopped responding	
09:16:49	75	0.09		1	1											End of Profile to FL090	
09:18:50																Start Run 4 @ FL090	
09:19:00	75	0.08		1	1												
09:21:00	20	0.09		1	1												
09:23:00	15	0.09		1	1												
09:24:55																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 5 from FL090	
09:25:28	15	0.10		1	1											FL100	
09:26:30	45	0.09	7	1	1											FL110	
09:27:27	30	0.10		1	1											FL120	
09:28:30	60	0.10		1	1											FL130	
09:29:42	25	0.08		1	1											FL140	
09:30:35																End of Profile 5 @ FL150	
																Start Profile 6 from FL150	
09:34:12	40	0.08	13	1	1											FL140	
09:36:28	80	0.10		2	2											FL130	
09:38:30	85	0.10		2	1											FL120	
																Start Run 5 @ FL127	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.20V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.5V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 20mw	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.0 V		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of flight:

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	082500 105200	Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	N	Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Ffssp.cal28022008.txt Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		Y
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = Blocks written = Bad reads =
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y Y N Y Y N	Start = End = Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Not processed since data is all noise Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	0 0 240000	Min size = Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B358_cvi_log

4/22/08 8:32:14 AM Startup OK
4/22/08 8:32:25 AM Horace signal good,
4/22/08 8:32:36 AM Lyman Zero at 8.30 UTC (ish)
4/22/08 8:32:41 AM PCASP signal
4/22/08 8:32:45 AM CPC signal
4/22/08 8:33:08 AM CPC signal
4/22/08 8:33:38 AM CPC signal
4/22/08 8:40:27 AM pressure pump reading not registering
4/22/08 8:40:48 AM Found a loose pipe before the first dririte canister
4/22/08 8:40:57 AM tightened up the pipe work
4/22/08 8:41:53 AM tightened up the pipe work
4/22/08 8:43:23 AM Will be operating most of the day in Aerosol mode (no cloud
forecast during sortie)
4/22/08 8:44:09 AM pressure pump turned off (now in aerosol mode)
4/22/08 8:44:22 AM another lyman zero
4/22/08 8:45:02 AM remove reference airflow to lyman, and reconnect sample flow
4/22/08 8:47:54 AM Lyman is now sampling ambient air
4/22/08 8:48:05 AM cwc ~ 5 G/M³
4/22/08 9:02:40 AM CPC CONDENSOR =2.5 ???
4/22/08 9:08:57 AM horace FEED OK, cpc OK, pcasp OK, LYMAN ok
4/22/08 9:09:03 AM CLOSE FOR T/O
4/22/08 10:19:07 AM BACK ABOVE 5000FT AND AT THE CONSOLE
4/22/08 10:28:17 AM BACK ABOVE 5000FT AND AT THE CONSOLE
4/22/08 10:28:31 AM BACK ABOVE 5000FT AND AT THE CONSOLE
4/22/08 10:31:30 AM START OF PROFILE 6, LOOK FOR DUST LAYER
4/22/08 10:41:11 AM turning for run into dust layer
4/22/08 10:51:34 AM CWC is now negative at this high dry region
4/22/08 10:52:20 AM begin descent profile
4/22/08 10:58:22 AM FL90
4/22/08 10:59:35 AM PCASP - noise in lower channels? ch2, ch3
4/22/08 10:59:49 AM start run
4/22/08 11:06:10 AM start run
4/22/08 11:06:24 AM start run
4/22/08 11:06:51 AM descend for fib
4/22/08 11:07:01 AM (CORR) descend for final run
4/22/08 11:07:08 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:07:29 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:07:35 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:07:38 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:08:08 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:08:11 AM Reduce PCASP flow
4/22/08 11:10:15 AM turning
4/22/08 11:11:02 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:11:25 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:11:34 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:11:40 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:13:50 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:14:00 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:14:04 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:14:08 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:15:01 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:15:06 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:15:13 AM run start 3kft
4/22/08 11:15:34 AM climb out of area, end of science

Flight:

B358

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B358

Date: 22 April 2008

Instruments

1. Mission Scientist Laptop – Not connecting to HORACE after T/O. Fitted Ethernet lead, then okay.
2. Video – Stopped 0927, program crashed, restarted recording at 0929Z. Crashed again at about 1035Z, restarted program.
3. Cloud Physics – SID2 noisy, otherwise okay
4. CVI – worked well

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

1 x ACAS

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 22/04/08

Flight No: B 358

Pre-Flighter: MS, DHA, SCD, PDR

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	Not fitted
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24				
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	Not fitted
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	UIS
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
		ICEX applied		
		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Flight B358 10:33:16

Heading 159 deg Speed 311 knots Height 13.1kft Press 616mb

Lat 52°18.0'N Long 3°18.0'E Wind 10 ms-1/ 41 deg

Temp -10.14C Dewpoint -40.7C

From start to now

Current values			
—	RADAR HEIGHT	8191.75	ft
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	52.85	ppb
—	TECO NO	0.49	ppb
—	TECO NO2	-0.4	ppb

Flight B358 10:31:13

Heading 159 deg Speed 305 knots Height 14.9kft Press 572mb

Lat 52°30.0'N Long 3°12.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 35 deg

Temp -13.91C Dewpoint -39.44C

From start to now

Current values			
+	OZONE MIXING RATIO	57.41	ppb
+	TECO NO	0.23	ppb
+	TECO NO2	0	ppb
+	TECO NOx	0.13	ppb

Flight B358 10:47:05
 Heading 69 deg Speed 184 knots Height 2.1kft Press 937mb
 Lat 51°48.0'N Long 4°6.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/81 deg
 Temp 7.74C Dewpoint 4.36C
 From start to now

Current values
 INU LONGITUDE 4.15 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
 INU LATITUDE 51.86 deg (+ve N)

Flight B358 10:34:21
 Heading 161 deg Speed 302 knots Height 11.9kft Press 645mb
 Lat 52°12.0'N Long 3°18.0'E Wind 6 ms-1/46 deg
 Temp -8.26C Dewpoint -35.31C
 From start to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 38061 secs All scroll time
 NEPH BLUE SP 0.63 m-1
 NEPH GREEN SP -0.27 m-1
 NEPH RED SP 0.63 m-1

Flight B358 10:19:35
 Heading 7 deg Speed 241 knots Height 11.6kft Press 654mb
 Lat 52°54.0'N Long 1°54.0'E Wind 10 ms-1/83 deg
 Temp -7.65C Dewpoint -35.06C
 From 09:22:41 to now

Current values
 STATIC PRESSURE 654.37 mb
 DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -7.65 deg C
 DEW POINT -35.07 deg C

Flight B358 10:47:04
 Heading 69 deg Speed 184 knots Height 2.1kft Press 937mb
 Lat 51°48.0'N Long 4°6.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/81 deg
 Temp 7.74C Dewpoint 4.36C
 From start to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 38823 secs All scroll time
 NEPH BLUE SP 72.32 m-1
 NEPH GREEN SP 52.49 m-1
 NEPH RED SP 33.34 m-1

Flight B358 10:17:15

Heading 359 deg Speed 215 knots Height 5.6kft Press 821mb

Lat 52°48.0'N Long 1°54.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 89 deg

Temp 3.41C Dewpoint -18.69C

From 09:22:41 to now

Current values		
++++	STATIC PRESSURE	821.39 mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	3.41 deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-18.7 deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B358:

Log	Reason
Flight Manager's Instrument Status log	No log available until database entries completed
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 May 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080422_b358_082724_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080422_b358_092921_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080422_b358_103708_25hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080422_b358_080017_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080422_b358_080139_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080422_b358_082710_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080422_b358_092912_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080422_b358_103659_25hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080422_b358_080150_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080422_b358_082715_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080422_b358_092915_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080422_b358_103702_25hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080422_b358_082721_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080422_b358_092919_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080422_b358_103705_25hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

?